

Alzheimer's Disease stage detection using MRI images for early diagnosis

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ABSTRACT: A neurodegenerative condition that progresses over time is Alzheimer's disease (AD). Alzheimer's disease will affect personality and conduct in addition to the most common symptoms, which include difficulty thinking, making judgments and decisions, and difficulty doing familiar tasks. The cause of AD development is not well understood. An individual suffering from Alzheimer's disease may experience extreme forgetfulness as the illness progresses and will be unable to conduct daily activities. The elderly are the predominant population affected by this incurable illness. The categorization procedure has used the deep learning methodology. AD detection involves the use of neuroimaging techniques such as PET and MRI scans. Deep learning algorithms are employed in conjunction with multi-model neuroimaging techniques to improve the categorization of Alzheimer's patients. In this study, we will classify images into three categories: normal cognitive function (NC), moderate cognitive impairment (MCI), and Alzheimer disease (AD) using MRI, PET scan, and CNN (convolution neural network

Keywords CNN (Convolution Neural Networks), Deep learning, SVM (Support Vector Machine), KNN (K-Nearest Neighbor), ABCD (Asymmetry, Border, Color, Diameter), SVM (Support Vector Machine), Dermoscopic, Pre-processing, Feature Extraction, Segmentation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease promotes brain cell deterioration, which shrinks the hippocampal region, shrinks the cerebral cortex, and enlarges the ventricles, all of which contribute to memory loss. An individual with Alzheimer's disease has trouble going about their daily lives. A patient's social life is impacted. According to estimates from the Alzheimer's Association, around 6 million Americans have the illness, making it the sixth most common cause of death in the country. In the US, AD was expected to cost \$277 billion in 2018. According to the organization, over the next few decades, early and correct diagnosis might result in savings of up to \$7.9 trillion in medical and care expenses. Early therapy for Alzheimer's disease can help prevent symptoms from being exaggerated. Early discovery of the condition is therefore beneficial. There is no drug that can halt or reverse AD's development. A number of tests, including a brief mental state assessment, physical and neuro biological exams, and a thorough history of the patient, are necessary for the proper diagnosis of

Alzheimer's disease. It makes sense to employ computer benefits like speed and precision to identify Alzheimer's disease as manual diagnosis is laborious and prone to human mistake.

Convolution, pooling, normalizing, and connection are the four primary layer types of convolutional neural networks, and they carry out the fundamental functions of these networks. The input image picture is produced by a range of convolutional filters to separate the characteristics present in those portions because of the Convolution Layer. By using the pooling layer to reduce the amount of data being processed, the network's sensitivity to the studied scene's all materials.

distortion is lessened. The two main techniques used in this layer are averaging, which averages the value, and max pooling, which selects the largest value inside the parsed window. The networks ability to handle nonlinear problems is increased by the data normalization process at the ReLED layer (Rectified Linear Units Layer). CNN is made up of several layers on progressively higher levels, but the findings are accommodated to the last layer, known as the Fully Connected Layer, in such a system. This layer allows for the various assignments by generating the final rating. CNN differs from traditional neural networks in that it has many more layers than the latter. The longest path between the input and output neurons in a neural network design is called its depth. Although the exact number of layers required to qualify a network as "deep" is unknown, it is generally accepted that a network with more than two hidden levels falls under this category. CNN reduces computation in comparison to a traditional neural network. Convolution greatly reduces processing complexity without sacrificing the meaning of the data. When it comes to picture categorization, they excel. They apply the same understanding to every picture location.

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a long-term illness that results in brain shrinkage and the death of brain cells. It might happen in middle or elderly age due to widespread brain deterioration. About 60–70% of instances of dementia are caused by AD. One of the most prevalent early symptoms of this disease is short-term memory loss. As the illness progresses, symptoms include behavioral and linguistic issues, confusion, mood fluctuations, loss of motivation, and ineffective self-care management. When a person's health deteriorates, they frequently experience psychological and emotional issues from society and family. The typical life expectancy upon diagnosis is fewer than nine years, despite the fact that the disease can advance at different rates.

In 2015, there were over 29.5 million cases of Alzheimer's disease globally. The majority of instances start in adults over 65, while 4% to 5% have an early beginning before then. In 2015, dementia was the cause of 1.9 million fatalities. One of the most expensive illnesses in wealthy nations is AD. Over 4 million individuals in India suffer with dementia in one way or another.

The number of AD patients is expected to quadruple by 2050. In the early stages of AD, there are medicinal therapies available to address the disease impact. However, because Alzheimer's disease progresses irreversibly, early detection of the illness is crucial from a clinical, social, and financial standpoint. The development of imaging and computational technology aided medical research in diagnosing diseases early on and initiating corrective treatment measures. Nevertheless, there is still a need for precise, quick computational techniques and algorithms to facilitate the simple, early identification of neurological illnesses. The brain experiences both anatomical and functional alterations as a result of AD. It produces anatomical and morphological patterns that are dynamically developing. It is possible to identify the novel alterations brought about by AD by examining these changes both qualitatively and quantitatively and contrasting them with the typical functions and characteristics of the human brain. The Alzheimer's and normal control cases are categorized as AD (Alzheimer's disease), MCI (Mild Cognitive Impairment), and NC (Normal Control) individuals based on the morphological and anatomical alterations. MCI is an intermediate stage between AD and Normal Controls. As a result, both quantitative and qualitative AD diagnosis is highly valuable in clinical settings as it may expedite treatment and enhance both the patient's and

their caregivers' quality of life. Due to several technological and clinical problems, the present state-of-the-art diagnostic approaches have limited efficacy in clinical settings. Moreover, only a limited set of methods are specifically designed for the early prediction of AD. This work proposes a state-of-the-art easy and early diagnosis scheme using Magnetic Resonance Images (MRI) with the help of advanced machine learning tools

and algorithms such as deep learning. This work proposes an automated (machine learning) system to predict AD from a dataset of normal control subjects and diseased subjects. It classifies the data into Normal, Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI), and Alzheimer's disease. It helps a radiologist or clinical practitioner to easily predict the given MRI image belongs to which category with a high accuracy level than the conventional classification prediction system.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

- 1] The Axial, Coronal, and Sagittal planes are the three perpendicular planes in which the author saw the 3D structural magnetic resonance images. They extracted features from each of the three orthogonal pictures using first order statistics for the gray and white matter. Following that, they computed a correlation matrix for feature extraction, and Principal Component Analysis, or PCA, was employed for feature reduction. In the end, they used logistic regression, AdaBoost, Naïve Bayes, and Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifiers for binary classification. Using the naïve bayes classifier, they were able to attain 99.9% accuracy on white matter.
- 2] To avoid information loss during 3D picture slicing into 2D, the author employed 3D structural MR-images. They constructed a 3D VGG variant CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) using the publically accessible datasets ADNI and OASIS for this study. With the ADNI and OASIS datasets, the accuracy of the binary classification of Alzheimer's disease was found to be $73.4\% \pm 0.04$ (mean, standard deviation) and $69.9\% \pm 0.06$ (mean, standard deviation), respectively.
- 3] After preprocessing these picture slices, the author utilized three to four from a single scan for each patient. The CNN network received training for classifying AD. Each of the four conv2D levels in the CNN architecture is followed by the max pool layer and the two fully linked layers. Three different activation function types were employed by the author: sigmoid, relu, and leaky relu, which prevented the vanishing gradient issue.
- 4] The author classified AD/NC using 3D CNN on FDG and AV-45 PET images. Following the network's training, the author provided photos to MCI subjects in order to determine whether or not these subjects would go on to acquire AD. For AD/NC, this approach achieves 96% accuracy; for MCI to AD conversion subjects, it achieves 84.2% accuracy.
- 5] The most helpful aspects of the structural magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) were extracted by the author using a deep convolutional neural network (DCNN). First, a rigid pipeline is used to preprocess the structural MRIs. Afterwards, we re-slice each volume and feed the resliced pictures straight into a DCNN rather than parcellating the regions of interest. The average accuracy for identifying the four phases of Alzheimer's is 94.5% for NC vs LMCI, 96.9% for NC versus AD, 97.2% for LMCI and AD, 97.81% for EMCI versus AD, and 94.8% for LMCI versus EMCI. Eventually, this is achieved. Results indicate that the DCNN performs better than current techniques.
- 6] The author used a deep convolutional neural network (DCNN) to extract the most useful information from the structural magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). The structural MRIs are first preprocessed using a strict workflow. Instead of parcellating the regions of interest, we reslice each volume and input the resliced images directly into a DCNN. For NC vs LMCI, 96.9% for NC versus AD, 97.2% for LMCI and AD, 97.81% for EMCI versus AD, and 94.8% for LMCI versus EMCI, the average accuracy in detecting the four phases of Alzheimer's disease is 94.5%. This is eventually accomplished. According to the results, the DCNN outperforms existing methods.
- 7] For every visit assessment, 30 2D slices in the axial plane above the eye are chosen, and these pictures are sent straight into CNN for feature extraction. The accuracy of this method's AD classification using random forest, SVM, and KNN following feature extraction is 0.88%, 0.95%, and 0.85% for random forest, SVM, and KNN, respectively. The images used in this project were from the MIRIAD collection.

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

Convolution Neural Networks(CNN) :

1- Image Acquisition: The digital camera attached to the laptop is used to take the pictures. More pre-processing is applied to the collected photos.

2- Image Pre-processing: Pre-processing is applied to the camera-captured photos in order to improve their quality. Pre-processing techniques might involve green masking, histogram equalization, color modification, and noise reduction, among other things. Here, we improve the image quality by applying the color modification approach. RGB images are converted to greyscale and high-strength image (HSI) to improve quality.

3- Image Segmentation : There are several approaches to image segmentation, including edge-based, neural network-based, clustering, and thresholding. The clustering method used in this implementation for picture segmentation is termed mean shift clustering. The sliding window approach is used by this technique to converge to the greatest dense area's center. Several sliding windows are used by this approach to converge to the greatest dense area. Algorithm for mean shift clustering The primary usage of this technique is the detection of extremely dense regions. Divided Picture

4- Feature Extraction:

An picture has several characteristics, the primary ones being color, texture, and form. Three features are being considered here: the color histogram, the texture, which is similar to color, and form.

5 : Classification Using CNN :

This module uses a convolution neural network classifier to classify these photos. A number of variables are combined to assess which features are relevant and identify distinguishing characteristics for crack detection.

CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

Neural network with many convolutional layers

Convolution Layer

The initial layer in feature extraction from an input picture is convolution. Convolution uses tiny squares of input data to learn visual attributes, preserving the link between pixels. A filter or kernel and an image matrix are the two inputs used in this mathematical technique.

- An image matrix (volume) of dimension **(h x w x d)**
- A filter **(f_h x f_w x d)**
- Outputs a volume dimension **(h - f_h + 1) x (w - f_w + 1) x 1**

Image matrix multiplies kernel or filter matrix

1	1	1	0	0
0	1	1	1	0
0	0	1	1	1
0	0	1	1	0
0	1	1	0	0

*

1	0	1
0	1	0
1	0	1

5 x 5 – Image Matrix
3 x 3 – Filter Matrix

Image matrix multiplies kernel or filter matrix

Next, as the output below illustrates, the convolution of a 5 x 5 image matrix multiplies with a 3 x 3 filter matrix to create a "Feature Map."

3 x 3 Output matrix

By applying several filters to a picture, convolution may carry out tasks like edge detection, blur, and sharpening. The sample below illustrates many convolution images created by applying various filter types (Kernels).

Strides

We advance the filters one pixel at a time starting at a stride of 1. We advance the filters by two pixels at a time when the stride is two, and so on. With a stride of 2, convolution would function as shown in the image below.

Stride of 2 pixels

Padding

There are situations where the filter does not suit the input image exactly.

- Use zero-padding to enlarge the image so that it fits.
- Remove the area of the picture where the filter was not compatible. Valid padding preserves just the valid portion of the picture.

Non Linearity (ReLU)

ReLU stands for Rectified Linear Unit for a non-linear operation. The output is $f(x) = \max(0, x)$. The objective of ReLU is to inject non-linearity into our ConvNet, which is why it is vital. Since non-negative linear numbers are what our ConvNet should learn from real-world data.

ReLU operation

ReLU can also be substituted with other nonlinear functions, such as sigmoid or tanh. Since ReLU outperforms the other two in terms of performance, the majority of data scientists utilize it.

Pooling Layer

When the photos are too big, the number of parameters would be decreased in the pooling layers portion. Spatial pooling, sometimes referred to as downsampling or subsampling, lowers each map's dimensionality while keeping crucial details. Several forms of spatial pooling are possible:

- Maximum pooling; Average pooling; and Total pooling

The biggest element from the corrected feature map is taken via max pooling. The average pooling might alternatively be determined by taking the biggest element. The total of each feature map element is referred to as sum pooling.

Max Pooling

Fully Connected Layer

Our matrix was flattened into a vector and sent into the layer we refer to as the FC layer, which is a fully connected layer similar to a neural network.

After pooling layer, flattened as FC layer

SComplete CNN architecture

IV.METHODOLOGY

- 1. MR images** are sent into the proposed system and are then classified as either PD or HC. There are a total of eight primary layers in the model. Convolution 1, max-pool 1, convolution 2, max-pool 2, convolution 3, dense layer 1, dense layer 2, and an output layer are the layers that make up this order. All three convolutional layers (Conv1, Conv2, and Conv3) and the two max-pooling layers (Max pool1, Max pool2) have kernel sizes of 3 by 3, producing 32 feature maps. These feature maps are learned by CNN, allowing CNN to distinguish between PD and HC in MR images. In CNN, pooling layers often come after convolutional layers. The convolutional layers of Conv1 and Conv2 with stride 1 and padding 0 are followed by two max-pooling layers of Max-pool 1 and Max-pool 2.
- 2. Preprocessing Techniques:** Normalization of Data The process of altering the range of pixel or voxel intensity values is called data normalization. To make the process of detecting tiny differences easier, it attempts to eliminate some variables in the data, such as variances in subject attitude or contrast between images. Examples of data normalizing techniques include zero-mean, unit variance normalization, $[-1, 1]$ rescaling, and $[0, 1]$ rescaling. In the current investigation, the final approach is used. It is clear how various normalizing techniques differ from one another. It shows an original image and the form that is produced when various data normalization techniques are used.
- 3. Proposed Classification Methods and Techniques:** Traditional machine learning techniques consist of three fundamental stages: feature extraction, feature reduction, and classification. The typical CNN then combines all of these phases. It is not necessary to do the feature extraction procedure manually while utilizing CNN. Iterative learning improves the weights of the early layers, which operate as feature extractors. CNN performs better than alternative classifiers.
- 4. Deep learning** With deep learning, an AI model learns how to solve categorization issues directly from a dataset— which may contain text, images, or audio. Neural network design is generally used to implement
- 5. deep learning.** The network will get deeper as the number of layers increases. Deep neural networks can have several layers, in contrast to standard neural networks, which typically have two or three layers. Artificial intelligence identification applications including computer vision, face recognition, natural language processing, voice recognition, social media filtering, and bioinformatics are especially well-suited for deep learning models. It has occasionally produced outcomes that are both on par with and superior than those of human experts.
- 6. When compared to other machine learning instruments, deep learning is state-of-the-art due to its accuracy.** The three technology domains have advanced to the point where this great degree of precision is possible. (i) Access to enormous collections of labeled data was made possible by the simple and open availability of big datasets (such ImageNet, Caltec101, and MNIST). (ii) High performance GPUs enable high computational power. It will speed up and shorten the training period for deep learning by improving the training of a big quantity of data. Pretrained models of deep neural networks (iii). The pre-trained deep neural network models (such AlexNet, VGG-16, and Resnet-50) may be retrained to complete new classification and pattern recognition tasks with the aid of the transfer learning approach.

7. The deep neural network must automatically identify which of the three categories represented in the collection of magnetic resonance images—AD (Alzheimer's disease), MCI (Mild Cognitive Impairment), and NC (Normal Control)—a random MR picture belongs to. The purpose of labeling the photos is to train the network. The deep neural network would then be able to begin to understand the unique aspects of the MR Image and pair them with the appropriate set of data with the use of this training data. After undergoing a transformation, each layer in the network transfers the data from the previous layer to the one after it. The network will learn more intricate and detailed information as it moves up the layers. The ability of the deep learning model to learn on its own is its most crucial feature. That is, the network will immediately learn from the provided data. As a result, neither the quantity nor the characteristics that are being learnt have any bearing on the person..

V .RESULTS

Predicted Output :

Fig 6.1 Generated Response

Fig 6.3 Generated Response For Image

VI.CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

To help physicians diagnose Alzheimer's disease earlier, we have developed software that can identify Alzheimer's from MRI scans and distinguish between the disease's various stages of severity. This work successfully created and deployed an automated machine learning tool that uses a deep learning algorithm to detect Alzheimer's disease. Additionally, the CNN models' performance levels were looked at. Deep learning predicts Alzheimer's disease with a high degree of accuracy—between 80 and 90 percent.

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